

PROPOSED ENHANCEMENT TRAINING-WORKSHOP DESIGN IN MODULE DEVELOPMENT FOR GRADE 4 TEACHERS

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Abstract. The study aimed to propose an enhancement training workshop design in module development for Grade 4 teachers in districts IV-A and IVB in San Carlos City Division during the school year 2021-2022. A typical Grade 4 teacher has a "very short" (1-5 years) teaching experience with MA/MS units and has attended school-level in-service training only. Based on the results of the study, the Grade 4 teachers in districts IV-A and IV-B are proficient along with the following factors namely: appropriateness, organization, mechanics, and design and layout. The teacher-respondents encountered serious problems in module development. There are significant relationships between the Grade 4 teachers' profile variables their level of proficiency and the extent of the seriousness of the problems encountered in module development and their level of proficiency. It is highly recommended that the proposed 3-day enhancement training workshop design be implemented by school heads to sustain or further enhance the level of proficiency of Grade 4 teachers in module development.

Keywords. Enhancement Training Workshop Design, Module Development, Level of Proficiency, Extent Seriousness

1 Introduction

Even before the outbreak of the global COVID-19 pandemic, the world was already confronting a "learning crisis." (World Bank 2019). In addition, countries around the world have expressed their desire to improve the accessibility of quality education for all people. With the aid of the United Nations (U.N.), this desire was addressed and stipulated in its Sustainable Development Goal number 4—"ensuring inclusive and equitable quality education and promoting lifelong learning opportunities for all." (Sustainabledevelopment.un.org, 2019).

With the spread of the virus, the education system is now facing an entirely new and massive crisis. According to the United Nations Educational, Scientific, and Cultural Organization (UNESCO), more than 87% of the world's student population—over 1.5 billion learners in 165 countries—have been affected by educational institutions' temporary closure. This scenario happened during World War II in many countries around the world in which schools and educational institutions went into lockdown at around the same time and for the same reason.

Extended school closures may cause a loss of learning in the short term and diminish human capital and economic opportunities for children and youth over the long term. Globally, school closures disproportionately hurt vulnerable and disadvantaged students who rely on schools for a range of social services, including health and nutrition. Nevertheless, their impact on education is likely to be most devastating in countries with already low learning outcomes, high dropout rates, and low resilience to shocks.

Faced with the COVID-19 pandemic, UNESCO launched The Global Education Coalition, a platform for collaboration and exchange to protect the right to education during this unprecedented disruption and beyond. It brings together more than 140 members from the United Nations family, civil society, academia, and the private sector to ensure that learning never stops.

Countries worldwide, specifically the education sectors, have launched different plans as an urgent response to ensure the continuity of education. Face-to-face learning engagement of learners and teachers within the school has been suspended due to the COVID-19 pandemic; that is why various modalities have been presented for the schools to adopt.

In the Philippines, for instance, the country continues to confront different issues brought about by the coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19) pandemic; the Department of Education (DepEd) is addressing the challenges in the basic education for

the school year 2020-2021 through its Basic Education Learning Continuity Plan (BE-LCP) under DepEd Order No. 012, s. 2020.

The Basis Education Learning Continuity Plan (BE-LCP) is consistent with the mandate of Section 1, Article XIV of the 1987 Constitution for the state to protect and promote the right of all citizens to quality education at all levels and take appropriate steps to make such education accessible to all. Under Section 6, Chapter 1 of Republic Act No. 9155, or the Governance of Basic Education Act of 2001, DepEd is vested with the authority, accountability, and responsibility for ensuring access to, promoting equity in, and improving the quality of basic education.

Hence, the BE-LCP aims to ensure the health, safety, and well-being of the learners, teachers, and personnel in this time of COVID-19, while finding ways for education to continue amidst the crisis. In particular, the BE-LCP has been designed with a legal framework responsive to the "new normal," keeping in mind the constitutional mandate to uphold all citizens' right to quality education at all times.

In addition, DepEd stated that when the COVID-19 pandemic struck the Philippines, strict community quarantine measures were implemented, including the prohibition of face-to-face learning.

In line with this, the learning delivery modalities that schools can adopt may be one or a combination of the following, depending on the local health conditions, the availability of resources, and the particular context of the learners in the school or locality. The following modalities are as follows: First on the list is face-to-face learning which refers to a modality where the learners and the teacher are both physically present in the classroom, and there are opportunities for active engagement, immediate feedback, and socio-emotional development of learners. Notably, this modality is feasible only in very low-risk areas with no history of infection, easily monitored external contacts, and teachers and learners living in the school's vicinity. Second is distance learning which refers to a modality where learning occurs between the teacher and the geographically remote learners during instruction. This modality has three types: Modular Distance Learning, Online Distance Learning, and Television/Radio-Based Instruction. This is most viable for independent learners and learners supported by periodic supervision of parents or guardians. Third, blended learning refers to a learning delivery that combines face-to-face with any, or a mix of, Modular Distance Learning, Online Distance Learning, and Television/Radio-Based Instruction. Blended Learning will enable schools to limit face-to-face learning, ensure social distancing, and decrease people's volume outside the home at any given time. Lastly, homeschooling aims to provide learners with quality basic education that qualified parents facilitate, guardians, or tutors who have undergone relevant training in a home-based environment. (DO 12, s. 2020) However, this modality will be the subject of a later DepEd issuance since several issues remain in its implementation, including licensed teachers' supervision and alignment with the standard curriculum.

Among the learning modalities mentioned, modular learning is the most popular type of distance learning. In the country, this learning modality is currently used by all public schools because, according to a survey conducted by the DepEd, learning through printed and digital modules emerged as the most preferred distance learning method of parents with children who are enrolled this academic year (Bernardo, J 2020). This is also in consideration of the learners in rural areas where the internet is not accessible for online learning.

The teacher takes the responsibility of monitoring the progress of the learners. The learners may ask the teacher for assistance via e-mail, telephone, text message, /or instant messaging, among others. Where possible, the teacher shall do home visits to learners needing remediation or assistance. Printed modules will be delivered to students, parents, or guardians by the teachers or through local government officials.

Since education is no longer held within the school, parents serve as partners of teachers in education. Parents play a vital role as home facilitators. Their primary role in modular learning is to establish a connection and guide the child. (FlipScience, 2020). According to DepEd, parents and guardians perform various roles in modular learning, such as Module-ator, Bundy-clock, and Home Innovator. As a Module-ator, they are the ones to get and submit the printed Self-Learning Modules (SLMs) from and to schools or barangay halls at the beginning and end of the week, depending on the agreement between the parents and the school. As a Bundy clock, they must check their child's schedule or workweek plan. Because of the number of subjects or activities to be done, they must see that it is being followed accordingly to

avoid cramming or delays in submission, affecting the child's performance. Lastly, as Home innovators, they must provide their children with a productive learning environment to focus on learning. It must be a well-lighted and well-ventilated space in the house, with little or no distraction.

The use of modules encourages independent study. One of the benefits of using modules for instruction is the acquisition of better self-study or learning skills among students. Learners engage themselves in learning the concepts presented in the module. They develop a sense of responsibility in accomplishing the tasks provided in the module. With little or no assistance from others, the learners progress on their own. They are learning how to learn; they are empowered (Nardo, 2017). Other advantages of modular instruction include more choices and self-pacing for learners, more variety and flexibility for teachers and staff, and increased instructional materials' adaptability.

Due to this pandemic, teachers, being the front liners in the school, undergo training and seminars for module development. Selected teachers were called to help prepare self-learning modules by subject area within a short period. Due to insufficient preparation time and limited training and seminars for module development, several issues regarding errors in some modules have been circulated on social networking sites and different media platforms, later criticized by netizens.

Numerous seminars at the division level were planned in preparation for the opening of classes, and different topics were discussed in connection with module development but because of the limited time given to the teachers for the module preparation, teachers have had a hard time making modules.

These training and seminars were done virtually through Google Meet and Zoom, but because these were done virtually, SDO-San Carlos City cannot guarantee the attendees' active participation since teachers' work does not only revolve around attending seminars and training. Numerous seminars with different topics were implemented highlighting the different modalities of learning like online distance learning and modular distance learning. This, there were no follow-up seminars focusing on module development done at the district or even at the school level due to the variety of topics presented and the need to complete all of the contents of the planned seminars and training, which is one of the reasons why few teachers only agreed to become module-writers and the rest could not accept the challenge because of limited knowledge in connection to module development. This is why the researcher is interested in this study because she is also one of the module writers of SDO-San Carlos City, who has experienced developing modules despite insufficient training and seminars attended in module development.

The opportunity for training and seminars in module development will encourage and motivate all teachers or if not most teachers to become module writers. This will also help the SDO-San Carlos City to have sufficient manpower in module development and most importantly this is for the learners who are the ultimate beneficiaries of all the training and seminars attended by the teachers.

2 Review of Related Literature

The study of Safi (2017) is closely related to the present study because his study found that having INSET is effective, and there is a need for training for teachers. His study also found the need for professional trainers to train the teachers toward implementing the said training.

The study of Cruthaka and Pinngern (2016) was related to the present study because the researcher proposed an enhancement training workshop design in module development for Grade 4 teachers. The recommendations made by Cruthaka and Pinngern in their study could help the researcher develop an effective enhancement training workshop in modular development.

The study of Tupas and Noderama (2020) is related to the present study because one of the statements of the problems of the study is the extent of the seriousness of the problems encountered by the Grade 4 teachers, and the study of Tupas and Noderama found out that teachers are not interested in applying what they have learned in INSET training because of various problems like instructional materials, classroom facilities, school building, etc. Knowing the findings of their study was of great help to the researcher in conducting her study.

Lastly, the studies of Yazon (2018), Torrefranca (2017), and Vergara (2017) are related to the present study since the output of the proposed enhancement training-workshop design is for the teachers to develop their module for use by the learners.

3 Research Methodology

3.1 Research Design

The descriptive-developmental method of research was used in this study. According to Sevilla (2008), the descriptive method is designed for the investigator to gather information about present existing conditions. The principal aim of employing this method is to describe the nature of a situation as it exists at the time of the study and to explore the cause of a particular phenomenon. In the descriptive survey, the information provides the answer to the question. To solve the problem, a questionnaire was used to gather the data needed. The study is also developmental because the researcher developed and proposed an enhancement training workshop design in module development for Grade 4 teachers of Districts IV-A and IV-B of the San Carlos City Division.

3.2 Sources of Data

The study was conducted in Districts IV-A and IV-B of the San Carlos City Division. District IV-A consists of seven public elementary schools located respectively at different barangays of San Carlos City namely: Barangay Abanon, Calobaoan, Nambocor, Caoayan Kiling, Guelew, Supo, and Tebag. Likewise, there are seven public elementary schools in District IV-B, covering: Barangay Bacnar, Balite Sur, Bolosan-Caingal, Magtaking, Mestizo Norte, Palospos, and Turac. There is a total of 14 public elementary schools and the total number of Grade 4 teachers based on the data gathered by the researcher from each of the Public Schools District Supervisors of the two districts is 28.

3.3 Statistical Treatment of Data

Frequency counts and percentages were used to determine the professional profile of Grade 4 teachers in Districts IV-A and IV-B in terms of their highest educational attainment, length of teaching experience as a Grade 4 teacher, and the highest level of in-service training in module development attended.

To determine the level of proficiency of Grade 4 teachers in module development along certain factors like appropriateness, organization and mechanics, design, and layout, the average weighted mean was employed, and the results were interpreted.

To determine the extent of the seriousness of the problems encountered by the teacher-respondents in module development along with personal-related problems, school-related problems, and family-related problems, the average weighted mean was computed and interpreted using a 4- 4-point Likert scale according to the mean limits.

To answer sub-problem 4 in determining the relationship between the profile of Grade 4 teachers and their level of proficiency as well as sub-problem 5 in determining the relationship between the extent of the seriousness of the problems encountered by Grade 4 teachers in module development and their level of proficiency, Pearson product-moment of correlation coefficient was first employed to determine the degree of relationship between the variables. The significance of the degree of the relationship was determined using appropriate statistical tests through Statistical Package for the Social Sciences. (SPSS)

4 Presentation, Analysis, and Interpretation of Data

4.1 Level of Proficiency of Grade 4 Teachers in Module Development

Table 3. Level of Proficiency of Grade 4 Teachers in Module Development
N=28

Factor	Average Weighted Mean (AWM)	DE
Factor 1: Appropriateness		
1. Uses content that is suitable to the learner's level of development.	3.07	Proficient
2. Creates specific objectives of the subject area intended.	3.29	Proficient
3. Uses a variety of questions highlighting the development of higher cognitive skills such as critical thinking, creativity, learning by doing, inquiry, problem-solving, etc.	3.14	Proficient
4. Develop content that is free of ideological, cultural, religious, racial, and gender biases and prejudices.	2.96	Proficient
5. Captivates the interest of the learners.	3.11	Proficient
Overall Weighted Mean	3.11	Proficient
Factor 2: Organization and Mechanics		
1. Presents in an engaging, interesting, and understandable way.	3.14	Proficient
2. Possess knowledge regarding the logical and smooth flow of ideas.	3.29	Proficient
3. Uses vocabulary that is adapted to target learners' likely experience and level of understanding.	3.32	Proficient
4. Know the length of sentences that are suited to the comprehension level of the learners.	3.14	Proficient
5. Makes use of sentences and paragraph structures that are varied and interesting to the target learners.	3.14	Proficient
Overall Weighted Mean	3.21	Proficient
Factor 3: Design and Layout		
1. Creates simple and easily recognizable illustrations.	3.36	Proficient
2. Can clarify and supplement the text/caption of the image or illustration	3.36	Proficient
3. Properly labels or caption the images or illustrations.	3.18	Proficient
4. Uses harmonious blending of illustrations and text	3.25	Proficient
5. Uses culturally relevant illustrations.	2.14	Less Proficient
Overall Weighted Mean	3.06	Proficient
General Overall Weighted Mean	3.13	Proficient

The proficiency level of Grade 4 teachers in districts IV-A and IV-B were determined and analyzed based on the following factors which include appropriateness, organization and mechanics, design, and layout.

Table 3 shows that Grade 4 teachers had the highest average weighted mean of 3.29 (Proficient) in contributing to the achievement of specific objectives. of the subject area. This means that the majority of Grade 4 teachers recognize the importance of setting objectives that are specifically tailored to the intended learners.

The lowest AWM generated was 2.96 (Proficient) on developing content that is free of ideological, cultural, religious, racial, and gender biases and prejudices. This means that Grade 4 teachers should carefully consider all the aforementioned factors to be fair and give due respect to all learners. The overall weighted mean of Appropriateness is 3.11 or Proficient. This means that the need for enhancement training workshops in module development are not generally required because they claim that they are proficient. However, they still need to continually enhance and update themselves with the latest trends, especially in creating content for the module. This backs up the findings of Safi (2017), who concluded that teachers should be encouraged to attend professional events to become more productive and efficient in various pedagogy and modern trends. Professional development, such as in-service training, is an important component of effective teaching and learning.

As reflected in the table, all indicators generated a "proficient" description. Of the five indicators, using appropriate vocabulary targeting the learner's experience and level of understanding has the highest AWM of 3.32 which pertains to the general level of difficulty of non-technical words used in terms of familiarity and abstractness. This implies that Grade 4 teachers have a wide variety of vocabulary terms that they use appropriately depending on the learners' level of understanding.

Indicators 1, 4, and 5, on the other hand, have the lowest AWM of 3.14 and are still classified as "proficient." These indicators were primarily concerned with how sentences are structured concerning learners' levels of interest and comprehension. This means that teachers must be familiar with sentence structures to effectively communicate or deliver instruction or messages to learners without confusion.

The overall weighted mean for Organization and Mechanics is 3.21 or proficient. This means that the need for an enhancement training workshop in module development is not generally required because they claim that they are proficient. However, they still need to continually engage themselves in finding resources or references to develop modules with correct vocabulary considering the level of the learner. This substantiated Liwei's (2017) assertion that grammar, as well as sentence and paragraph structure teaching, should be prioritized to motivate teachers' communicative competence and the overall development of language skills. Teachers should put in a lot of effort to improve their students' communicative skills. The accuracy with which teachers use grammar, sentence, and paragraph structures determines their language skills proficiency, without which language skills cannot develop healthily and systematically.

Table 3 shows that Grade 4 teachers had the highest average weighted mean of 3.25 (Proficient) in using a harmonious blending of illustrations and texts. This implies that teachers consider the combination of elements to accent its similarities and bind the picture parts into a whole. The lowest AWM generated was 2.14 (Less Proficient) on using culturally relevant illustrations. This indicator is required as

teachers use knowledge, prior experiences, frame of references, and performance style of ethnically diverse students to make learning more relevant and effective to them. It got the lowest AWM because the teachers said that it takes some time to find or illustrate culturally relevant pictures or illustrations.

The overall weighted mean for Design and Layout is 3.06 or proficient. This means that the need for enhancement training workshops in module development are not generally required because they claim that they are proficient. However, they still need to participate in and attend seminars related to basic layout applications or even art activity training for them to learn the different techniques on how to properly label pictures and or illustrations and know the basic principles of art.

The General Overall Weighted Mean of the three factors in the level of proficiency is 3.13, which denotes proficiency. The result indicates that Grade 4 teachers are proficient in module development, but it also indicates that there is room for growth to improve their level of proficiency. To improve the level of proficiency of Grade 4 teachers, an enhancement training workshop is proposed.

4.2 Extend of Seriousness of the Problems Encountered by the Teacher-Respondents

It can be gleaned from Table 4 that all indicators under personal-related problems are described as "Serious". Moreover, indicator 2 on lack of preparation in module development has the highest AWM of 3.36 which means that most of the teacher-respondents believed that teacher-writers should be prepared in all aspects of module development. The findings of this study are supported by an article published by the National Center for Education and Statistics (2016), which stated that teachers' feelings of preparedness are one important indicator of their readiness to meet the challenges that come with their profession. Most teachers felt "moderately" or "somewhat" prepared for most training requirements, according to the results of a survey; only a few teachers felt "very well prepared" for many of the activities. Additionally, teachers' feelings of preparedness may reveal how well opportunities for continued learning have prepared them to teach.

Table 4 shows that Grade 4 teachers had the highest average weighted mean of 3.39 on lack of in-service training for teachers in module development, which showed that this indicator posed a serious problem they encountered in module development. This supported the findings of the study by Safi (2017) because he found out that having INSET is effective, and there is a need for training for teachers. His study also found the need for professional trainers to train the teachers toward implementing the said training.

Table 4. The Extent of Seriousness of the Problems Encountered by the Teacher-Respondents in Module Development
N=28

Problems Encountered	Average Weighted Mean (AWM)	DE
Personal-related		
1. Too many teaching assignments in different subject areas	2.96	Serious
2. Lack of preparation	3.36	Serious
3. Lack of experience in preparing modules	3.25	Serious
4. Unfamiliarity with basic layout applications	2.75	Serious
Overall Weighted Mean	3.08	Serious
School-related		
1. Lack of support from the school administration	3.12	Serious
2. Lack of in-service trainings for teacher in module development	3.39	Serious
3. Too many designated coordinators	3.07	Serious
4. Numerous school-related tasks	3.11	Serious
Overall Weighted Mean	3.17	Serious
Family-related		
1. Lack of support from the family members	2.79	Serious
2. Unbalanced home and work-life	3.07	Serious
3. Too many responsibilities in the family	3.00	Serious
4. Do not have quality time for the family	3.37	Serious
Overall Weighted Mean	3.06	Serious
General Overall Weighted Mean	3.34	Serious

On the contrary, lack of support from the administration has the lowest AWM of 2.71 and is described as “serious”, this proved that school administration plays a vital role in motivating the teachers to attend or join the training, seminars, and or workshops. This result substantiated the findings of the study by Safi (2017) titled "Teacher's Views about Effectiveness of the In-Service Training" which found that generally, teachers feel the need to participate in INSET Programs for their professional development. The respondents believed that scheduling and planning for the INSET should be made in close coordination with the school administration.

School-related problems have an overall weighted mean of 3.07, indicating that it is serious. As a result of the findings, it can be concluded that school-related problems must be addressed and considered when proposing an enhancement training workshop in module development.

It can be gleaned from the same table that an unbalanced home and work life has the highest AWM of 3.07, which implies that teacher-respondents observed that module development will constantly result in an imbalance of their home and work life. This result substantiated the study of Panchanatham (2011) in which he found out that role overload, dependent care issues, quality of health, problems in time management, and lack of proper support are the major factors causing an imbalance in the work and personal life of a person.

The General Overall Weighted Mean of the aforementioned problems is 3.34, which is considered serious. This reflects the common issues that a teacher encounters when developing a module; these issues must be taken into account when designing an enhancement training workshop so that teachers can create an effective module for their learners.

4.3 Relationship Between the Professional Profile of Grade 4 Teachers and Their Level of Proficiency

Table 5. Relationship between the professional profile of Grade 4 teachers and their level of proficiency

Level of Proficiency	Highest Educational Attainment				Length of Teaching Experience as Grade 4 Teacher				Highest Level of In-Service Training in Module Development Attended			
	r-value	interpretation	p-value	decision	r-value	interpretation	p-value	decision	r-value	interpretation	p-value	decision
Appropriateness	0.861	high positive correlation	0.0608	Accept Ho	0.8877	high positive correlation	0.0445	Reject Ho	0.9145	very high positive correlation	0.0296	Reject Ho
Organization and Mechanics	0.8286	high positive correlation	0.8295	Accept Ho	0.2531	negligible correlation	0.6812	Accept Ho	0.1434	negligible correlation	0.818	Accept Ho
Design and Layout	0.5448	moderate positive correlation	0.3423	Reject Ho	0.6845	moderate positive correlation	0.2023	Reject Ho	0.8743	high positive correlation	0.0524	Reject Ho

critical value: 0.729 level of significance: 0.05

The level of proficiency was related to the highest educational attainment of Grade 4 teachers. Based on Table 5, the p-value of appropriateness (0.0608) and organization and mechanics (0.8295) is greater than the significance level $\alpha = 0.05$. Therefore, the null hypothesis was accepted, in addition, there was a highly positive relationship found between appropriateness, organization, and mechanics and their highest educational attainment. However, design and layout have a moderate positive correlation with the highest educational attainment. Moreover, design and layout have a p-value of 0.3423 which is lower than the significance level of 0.05, therefore, the null hypothesis was rejected because there was a moderate positive correlation found between design and layout to highest educational attainment. The findings of the study imply that the highest educational attainment affects the level of proficiency of grade 4 teachers more specifically in the appropriateness, organization, and mechanics.

The level of proficiency was related to the length of teaching experience of Grade 4 teachers. It can be gleaned from Table 6 that the p-value of organization and mechanics (0.6812) is greater than the significance level $\alpha = 0.05$. Therefore, the null hypothesis was accepted, moreover, there was a negligible or no relationship found between organization and mechanics and the length of teaching experience as a Grade 4 teacher. However, the p-value of appropriateness (0.0445) and design and layout (0.2023) is lower than the significance level $\alpha = 0.05$. Therefore, the null hypotheses were rejected, because there was a high positive correlation found between appropriateness to the length of teaching experience as a Grade 4 teacher and a moderate positive correlation between design and layout to the length of teaching experience as a Grade 4 teacher. It is worth noting that the length of teaching experience as a Grade 4 teacher is correlated with their level of proficiency more specifically in the appropriateness and design and layout factors.

The level of proficiency was related to the highest level of in-service training in module development attended by Grade 4 teachers. It can be gleaned from Table 6 that the p-value of organization and mechanics (0.818) is greater than the significance level $\alpha = 0.05$. Therefore, the null hypothesis was accepted, moreover, there was a negligible or no relationship found between organization and mechanics and the highest level of in-service training in module development attended by Grade 4 teachers. However, the p-value of appropriateness (0.0296) and design and layout (0.0524) is lower than or equal to the significance level $\alpha = 0.05$. Therefore, the null hypotheses were rejected, because there was a very high positive correlation found between appropriateness and the highest level of in-service training in module development attended by Grade 4 teachers and a high positive correlation between design and layout to the highest level of in-service training in module development attended by Grade 4 teachers.

4.4 Relationship Between the Extent of the Seriousness of the Problems Encountered by the Teacher-Respondents and Their Level of Proficiency

The level of proficiency was related to the personal-related problems of Grade 4 teachers. Based on Table 6, the p-value of appropriateness (0.769) and organization and mechanics (0.3452) is greater than the significance level $\alpha = 0.05$. Therefore, the null hypothesis was accepted, in addition, there was a negligible or no relationship found between appropriateness and personal-related problems. However, organization and mechanics have a moderate positive correlation with personal-related problems. Moreover, design and layout have a p-value of 0.004364 which is lower than the significance level of 0.05, therefore, the null hypothesis was rejected because there was a very high positive correlation found between design and layout to the personal-related problems. The findings of the study imply that the personal related problems affect the level of proficiency of grade 4 teachers more specifically in the design and layout factor.

Table 6. Relationship between the extent of the seriousness of the problems encountered by the teacher-respondents and their level of proficiency

Level of Proficiency	Personal-related problems				School-related problems				Family-related problems			
	r-value	interpretation	p-value	decision	r-value	interpretation	p-value	decision	r-value	interpretation	p-value	decision
Appropriateness	0.1824	negligible correlation	0.769	Accept Ho	0.1173	negligible correlation	0.8509	Accept Ho	0.0527	negligible correlation	0.9329	Accept Ho
Organization and Mechanics	0.5421	moderate positive correlation	0.3452	Accept Ho	0.4939	low positive correlation	0.3977	Accept Ho	0.4497	low positive correlation	0.4473	Accept Ho
Design and Layout	0.9763	very high positive correlation	0.00436	Reject Ho	0.9725	very high positive correlation	0.00545	Reject Ho	0.9823	very high positive correlation	0.00282	Reject Ho

critical value: 0.729

level of significance: 0.05

The level of proficiency was related to the school-related problems of Grade 4 teachers. It can be gleaned from Table 6 that the p-value of appropriateness (0.8509) and organization and mechanics (0.3977) is greater than the significance level $\alpha = 0.05$. Therefore, the null hypothesis was accepted, moreover, there was a negligible or no relationship found between appropriateness and school-related problems. However, organization and mechanics have a low positive correlation with school-related problems. Furthermore, design and layout have a p-value of 0.005452 which is lower than the significance level of 0.05, therefore, the null hypothesis was rejected because there was a very high positive correlation found between design and layout to the school-related problems. It is worth noting that the school-related problems must be taken into consideration about the level of proficiency of grade 4 teachers more specifically in the design and layout factor.

The level of proficiency was related to the family-related problems of Grade 4 teachers. It can be observed from Table 6 that the p-value of appropriateness (0.9329) and organization and mechanics (0.4473) is greater than the significance level $\alpha = 0.05$. Therefore, the null hypothesis was accepted, moreover, there was a negligible or no relationship found between appropriateness and family-related problems. However, organization and mechanics have a low positive correlation with school-related problems. Furthermore, design and layout have a p-value of 0.002819 which is lower than the significance level of 0.05, therefore, the null hypothesis was rejected because there was a very high positive correlation found between design and layout to the family-related problems. It is worth noting that family-related problems must be taken into consideration concerning the level of proficiency of grade 4 teachers more specifically in the design and layout factor.

5 Conclusion and Recommendation

Given the findings, the following conclusions were drawn. A typical Grade 4 teacher has been in the profession for 1 to 5 years and is pursuing professional development through graduate studies and school-level in-service training. Based on the results of the study, the Grade 4 teachers in districts IV-A and IV-B are proficient along with the following factors namely: appropriateness, organization and mechanics, and design and layout. The extent of the seriousness of problems encountered by the Grade 4 teachers in module development is serious. Based on the findings of the study, there is a significant relationship between the level of proficiency of Grade 4 teachers and their professional profile. There was a significant relationship found between the extent of the seriousness of the problems encountered by the teacher-respondents in module development and their level of proficiency. An enhancement training workshop could be developed to sustain or further enhance the level of proficiency of Grade 4 teachers in module development.

Based on the above conclusions, the following recommendations offered a possible course of action. Grade 4 teachers should continue to pursue their higher education. Grade 4 teachers should continuously strive to improve their level of proficiency by attending enhancement training workshops. The problems that Grade 4 teachers face must be addressed or taken into consideration when proposing an enhancement training/workshop in module development. The three-day enhancement training workshop proposed in this study should be implemented by the school heads to sustain or further improve the level of proficiency of Grade 4 teachers in developing modules effectively. It is recommended that the proposed enhancement training/workshop for Grade 4 teachers should be adopted by other districts. Similar studies should be conducted to propose an enhancement training workshop design in module development for teachers in other grade levels.

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